

Progress Report Space4You

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility

DELIVERABLE D3.2.c

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP

PROJECT [Space4You]

SPOKE 1 - Aerospazio e mobilità sostenibile

DELIVERABLE D3.2.c

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	26/03/2024	Initial draft	All
1.0	22/04/2024	Complete version	Fabio Dovis, Sabrina Corpino
1.1	24/04/2024	Final version	Fabio Dovis, Sabrina Corpino

REPORTING PERIOD

Period covered: from [01/11/2023] to [30/04/2024]

Periodic report date and version: 26/04/2024, [version No 1]

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

.....	
NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile	1
Glossary	4
1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS	5
1.1 OBJECTIVES.....	5
1.2 WORK CARRIED OUT PER RM IN THE REPORTING PERIOD	6
1.2.1 Research Module 0.....	6
1.2.2 Research Module 1.....	10
1.2.2 Research Module 2.....	19
1.2.2 Research Module 3.....	27
1.2.2 Research Module 4.....	30
2. IMPACT.....	34
3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc)	35
4. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE).....	36
5. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE).....	36
6. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART.....	37

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The proposed laboratory, Space4You, shall tackle the challenges stemming out from the great attention devoted by the industry to Space and the consequential opportunities. The initial set-up of the lab addressed several different aspects related to the consolidation of the research work of the different teams and the coordination in a unified framework able to provide solutions for increasing the capabilities and outcomes of small satellites missions.

In particular the work is developed in the areas of:

- Design of space architectures for supporting innovative applications and services
- Development of technologies, materials, equipment, and processes for preparation and sustainable implementation of new applications
- Solutions for increasing autonomy of space habitats

As part of the Research Booster methodology of NODES, Space4You will carry out applied research activities with and for companies, to ensure an effective interaction between leading universities and research centers, scientific and industrial associations, important players from the industry, society, and policy makers. It will nurture ideas, inventions, and innovations generated in universities and transfer them to the industrial and social networks, fostering the relations, synergies, and cross-fertilization between different sectors.

During the reporting period, all tasks have been started within all Research Modules, and several results of the research activity have been produced, such as papers presented at conferences and journal articles, databases, and preliminary lab models. The details of the activities and of the achievements are given in Section 1.2 and in the annexes.

1.2 WORK CARRIED OUT PER RM IN THE REPORTING PERIOD

1.2.1 Research Module 0

Research Module n.0	Start month: M1				End month: M36			
Title: SETUP AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SPACE4YOU LAB								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y - Partially								
RM Leader	PolITO							
Partners involved	Polito	UniTo	Links	Poliba				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	8,3	3,31	1,42					
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>Activities to coordinate the research teams and to set up the distributed laboratory. Applied research activities that are functional to a better understanding of the dynamics of technology transfer and new business creation in the new space industry.</p>								
<u>Task 0.1 Lab setup and management</u>								
PolITO/DET and DIMEAS								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work on D4 • Preparation of periodic progress reports (M18) • Preparation of the dissemination material presented to the companies during the dissemination events, maintenance of a collaborative tool for documents management and meeting organization through a dedicated Microsoft Teams group involving all the participants in the project • Organization of periodic internal meetings and a general assembly of the flagship on March 15, 2024 • Cooperation with other Spokes of NODES for the coordination of the professional education activities • Dissemination and engagement activities towards the aerospace companies of the NODES ecosystem 								
All partners/Research teams								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to internal meetings to present and coordinate the different research activities. • Contribution to D4 • Establishment of procurement procedures for the improvement of new instrumentation for the research labs 								

Task 0.2 Ecosystem development

PoliTO/DIGEP:

Research activities related to the analysis of the determinants of commercial success of European aerospace startups were completed during the reporting period. In addition to the two datasets "SpaceStartups" and "SpaceInvestors," the third database "PatentSpace" related to patent applications in space technologies is nearing completion. In the last month, work has begun on the construction of a fourth dataset "RegionSpace," this dataset collects information about the main players in the space sector, projects developed and related to the space sector, and spatial information, which can enable a timely mapping of the space ecosystems present in Europe. These data will be used in the development of a fifth paper, related to entrepreneurial ecosystems in Europe.

Such data have been used for the development of 3 papers, outlined below.

The first paper empirically addresses the role of founders' characteristics on the firm's performance for deep-tech startups operating in the New Space domain. This paper has been concluded and submitted to Journal of Business Research.

The second paper provides an in-depth review of extant studies in the economics of innovation and management literature on the aerospace industry, with a focus on a key innovation driver for the industry, namely sustainability of space activities. This paper is actually under review to Sustainable Development Journal.

The third paper seeks to investigate the role of patents filed in Europe in space and their applications. Specifically, we want to identify the different applications of space patents in fields not typically space and their dual use. The analyses will be based on the tracking of patent citations patterns as a proxy of underlying knowledge flows.

PoliBA/DMMM: Analysis of emerging business models in the new space economy. The activity focused on the study and analysis of the business model of spaceports. Spaceports have a relevant role in the new space economy value chain as they provide facilities for the upstream sector as well as collect data for the downstream sector. As a first step, the research team identified all spaceports worldwide, including the active ones, the dismissed ones, and the ones that are still under construction. Next, the research team decided to focus on the active spaceports and started collecting data in order to understand their business models. Data collection relied on multiple secondary sources. The data analysis was an iterative process and a collaborative effort within the research team that involved multiple meetings until an agreement about the business models' canvas of the spaceports investigated was reached. Next, the business models were analyzed to identify commonalities and differences among them. The results encompass a description of the

spaceports analyzed and the development of a business model canvas for each of them. Furthermore, some patterns within these business models were identified based on the similarities among specific building blocks of the canvas (e.g., value proposition, customer segments, key partners). Finally, the activity also included an update of the literature review with the most recent scientific developments.

Task 0.3 Assessment and sustainability

Polito/DIGEP: This task is meant to support the evaluation the project's results and put them into a broader perspective of future exploitation, while also planning future activities according to the availability of the laboratory and its possible growth.

During the reporting period, the objectives were pursued by collecting data and conducting an updated literature review to highlight key innovation trends in the industry.

Output and results

Datasets creation:

1. "SpaceStartups": This is a new database containing information on 339 EU-based startups that were founded in the past 10 years and are operating within the space sector. We collected this data from the Dealroom database.
2. "SpaceInvestors": We have compiled data on VC and corporate investors in Europe who have made equity investments in aerospace startups. Most of our information comes from Dealroom as a data source.
3. "PatentSpace": The completed database is expected to contain approximately 25,000 patents filed with the European Patent Office over the last 10 years.
4. "RegionSpace": This dataset is under construction; the final version will contain a set of indicators needed to map and assess the entrepreneurial space ecosystem. These indicators will be collected at the regional NUTS3 level for a time horizon of about 10 years.

Deviations (if applicable):

The working group that will implement the website and knowledge portal was identified and the content to be included on the site was selected. The deliverable D4 (website and knowledge portal) has been delayed due to issues in the configuration of a proper infrastructure to host the portal. Notwithstanding the technical problem related to the implementation and deployment of the portal, the content of the web pages is under preparation.

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Finalisation of D4
- Completion of the database PatentSpace on patent applications at European level.

- Completion of the database RegionSpace on patent applications at European level.
- Completion of the econometric paper that through the exploitation of the PatentSpace database analyzes the extent of technology transfer from space to terrestrial activities and vice-versa.
- Development of an econometric paper that through the exploitation of the RegionSpace database.

1.2.2 Research Module 1

Research Module n.1	Start month: M4			End month: M36			
Title: DESIGN							
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y - partially							
RM Leader	PoliTO						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBA			
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	1.92	3.11	1.43				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
Research studies to support the DESIGN phase of space systems and missions.							
 <i>Task 1.1 Concurrent & virtual design</i>							
<p>PoliTO/DIMEAS (STAR): The main drivers of the Concurrent Engineering System (CES) are: 1) reusability of the facility across multiple projects, 2) traceability of requirements, 3) applicability of the facility across project phases (ideally up to phase B/PDR), and 4) usability of the facility by multiple users/operators in a distributed environment.</p> <p>The CES has been improved by the development of tools to support the design phases of space systems. These tools are: 1) calculation modules for the early design analyses, and 2) procedures step-by-step for the whole design process. A CubeSat mission for Earth Observation has been identified as reference use case for the validation of the CES tools.</p> <p>The CubeSat Technologies database (CUTE-DB) first draft has been completed, considering the information available on the market to date. Continuous updating activities will be performed to guarantee a CUTE-DB consistent with the market possibilities.</p>							
 <i>Task 1.2 Simulation models</i>							
<p>PoliTO/DISMA: Many practical applications require to simulate physical phenomena occurring in complex domains, i.e. domains characterized by the presence of multiple interfaces, or presenting features with characteristic sizes on different length scales. This is the case, for example, of structural simulations of objects with a layered structure, or with fiber reinforcements. Numerical tools for this kind of simulations still rely, in large part, on standard approaches based on homogenization techniques or on computational meshes that need to conform to the interfaces. Both these approaches have limitations that need to be addressed. Novel techniques have been proposed and further developed within this project, based either on the use of polygonal polyhedral meshes to easily create conforming meshes, either based on innovative coupling approaches that do not rely on mesh conformity. In the reporting period, in particular, the group focused on the application of the extended finite element methodology to 3D-1D coupled</p>							

problems, described via an optimization based domain decomposition method on non conforming mesh. Suitable enrichment basis functions have been selected and ad-hoc quadrature rules have been investigated for their numerical integration This research led to a publication and to a pre-print, currently under review for possible publication.

PoliTO/DIMEAS: As far as the studies for simulation modelling techniques for thermal systems are concerned, commercial tools for thermal analysis have been adapted to consider the effects of the lunar soil thermal radiation on the futuristic infrastructures on the Moon surface (power generation systems, habitats, rovers and mechatronics, etc..) inspired to the NASA ARTEMIS scenario. In the last period of time, the study focused on the choice of materials with which to carry out the best heat exchange in terms of radiators and thermal bands connecting radiant panels assembled in deployable structures. Some preliminary calculations were carried out on radiant and conductive nodes models using a commercial calculation tool.

LINKS/CPE: In literature, several approaches to perform the analysis of high-resolution images from a satellite constellation can be found, with a particular focus on the creation of a 3D model that can be used as a basis for a twin digital model. With standard approaches, the computational time becomes too high when dealing with very high precision images covering large areas, therefore a HPC approach is required. Among the possibilities, we tested a solution provided by nFrames called SURE. The solution was tested on images representing Parco Dora in Torino, with the construction of the 3D model of the park. Upon validation, the algorithms are being optimized to allow the scalability of the approach to a wider area, allowing the realization of the 3D model of an entire city. This model can be one of the building blocks for a digital twin model to support SMEs in the development of DSS tools as well as public administration in the definition of innovative strategies for city management.

UNITO/Math: This report outlines the progress made in employing computational methods to explore symmetric solutions for the N-body problem. The focus has been on developing algorithms to analyze and classify orbits, coming from SymOrb routine, based on their shape and stability properties, with the ultimate goal of generating new orbits through optimization techniques. The current results include the following new achievements: An extensive database has been established, comprising over 1000 distinct solutions for the N-body problem (specifically, solutions have been generated for configurations involving three bodies in both two and three dimensions); Algorithms to compute the Morse index and Floquet indicators of orbits have been developed and tested (the computed indices and indicators are utilized to assign labels to orbits, facilitating their clustering based on similarity); Progress on construction of visualization tools to

display the solutions found, have been made. A portion of the project's codebase is on GitHub. The private repository, hosted at <https://github.com/LimenResearch/norbit>.

PoliBA/DIMMM: The recent activities of POLIBA team concerned the implementation of the state-to-state model for neutral air mixture in the last 3D version of the code. Verification with the already validated 2D code have been carried on with optimal results for generic nitrogen, oxygen or neutral air mixtures. This represents the starting point for the extension to 11 species air mixture which involves charged atoms and molecules. Before starting the development of such a model, a preliminary phase has been focusing on the verification of the well-known macroscopic model for this kind of mixture, proceeding with the implementation of the two-temperature model proposed by Chul Park, which is very common in the hypersonic community. Not least, the extension of the transport model has been carried on, in order to account for heavy species/charged species collisions to evaluate viscosity, conductivity and diffusivity of the mixture. The activity is ongoing, with the timing provided at the beginning of the project.

In the meanwhile, macroscopic approach has been implemented also for oxygen/carbon compounds, typical of Mars atmosphere. In this way, the code is able to simulate re-entry flows for the “red planet” too. Needless to say, also for these mixtures, diffusion coefficient database has been updated and verified.

Lastly, the third part of the activity concerned the implementation and verification of a classical turbulence modeling employing a RANS (Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes) approach, namely, the two-equation k- ω SST (Shear Stress Transport) model. This model is widely used for hypersonic applications since it is cheap and easy to implement. However, some drawback raised from the implementation. First of all, an analysis on the temporal treatment of the source terms has been performed, in order to assess the influence of the numerical scheme on the final results. A semi-implicit, decoupled point iterative scheme (Gauss-Seidel) has been found suitable for such problems, providing results in excellent agreement with classical fully coupled implicit schemes. Secondly, an analysis about the expression of turbulent kinetic energy production term raised other issues, related to the expression of the closing terms of the model, specifically concerning the production term; further analyses are currently being performed.

[Task 1.3 ICT technologies](#)

Polito/DET: A general taxonomy of simulation tools for satellite networks have been devised, by which it was possible to classify 14 different network simulators/emulators, either open-source or commercial, based on more than 40 different criteria. In particular, specific information has been gathered about the scalability of the simulators in terms of number of satellites, in order to understand the possible applicability of the tools for large mega constellations. The taxonomy has

shown a different tradeoff between accuracy of the communication model and scalability for each tool, suggesting that the optimal choice must be tailored specifically to the considered scenario.

LINKS/CPE: During the previous reporting period, a server rack, based on an Open Stack architecture, has been configured. The servers, equipped with both high-performance CPUs and GPUs, has been configured as an HPC node to provide the necessary hardware resources to run simulations and/or to develop digital twin models.

During this reporting period, the activities focused on the development of innovative algorithms for the analysis of images, with a special focus for the images coming from satellites. The algorithms are being developed using a Cloud-Edge-IoT approach, exploiting the hardware potentialities of platforms based on nVidia Xavier Jetson. This solution allows to integrate data from local sensors with data from satellite images to provide a more comprehensive view of the surrounding environment and a support to the definition of a digital twin. Furthermore, such solution can be used to develop specific applications to support DSS systems or integrated into robotic platforms to enhance their capabilities.

Task 1.4 Generic technologies

Polito/DIMEAS (STAR): Novel visual navigation algorithms for proximity operations of small distributed systems in safety-critical context have been designed. The algorithms have been tailored to a specific use case: a nanosatellite performing a rendezvous and docking mission with a larger mothercraft in Low Earth Orbit.

Polito/DIMEAS: Leveraging on the background experience of the Photonext interdepartmental center the optic measurement of the temperature of space subsystems has been thorough, in particular, the FBG sensing technology. Some FBG sensors packaging techniques have been specifically designed for the temperature measurement of radiators, windows and tanks of lunar infrastructures and power generation systems.

Some proposed sensors packaging solution for the thermal monitoring by FBG of transparent windows of spacecraft have been proposed. A preliminary thermal testing of specimens into a thermal chamber has been conducted to allow the model validation and to test the suitability of the proposed packaging techniques. A possible communication network for the distribution of the sensors information has been conceived to allow thermal management and control activities. In particular, the share of the information via a WiFi network with augmented reality tools has been conceived to support the astronauts in decision making.

A prototype (a transmission antenna and its associated electronic circuit connected on a digital bus) was developed, based on 4G technology to simulate a possible lunar equivalent system for

WiFi sharing of information from hundreds of fibre-optic sensors in order to implement specific monitoring functions.

PoliTO/DISEG: During the reporting period, research conducted at the ArtIStE - Artificial Intelligence in Structural Engineering lab at DISEG Department focused on the development of parametric models for designing potential space habitats. Various solutions combining inflatable structures with gridshell-type structures were explored. These parametric models were designed to be optimized using multi-objective optimization algorithms, with the goal of minimizing the amount of material required for construction. Additionally, form-finding methodologies were employed to identify structural optima and further reduce material usage. Experiments were also conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of augmented reality media in creating three-dimensional models of these space habitats, which were subsequently connected to 3D holographic rotating projectors for visualizing the structures.

UniTO/Chemistry: During the reporting period, investigations and syntheses about advanced materials (i.e. organic dyes and electrolytes) for the development of innovative solar cells have been continued. Concerning organic dyes, two novel molecular structures have been synthesized and characterized for application in p-type dye-sensitized solar cells (p-DSSCs). The design of these two new molecules has been inspired by the state-of-art dye PMI-6 T-TPA. In particular, a specific engineering of the thiophene-based central core has been considered to favour structural planarity between an oligothiophenic π -spacer (a sexithiophene), and the acceptor and donor units made by peryleneimide (PMI) and triphenylamine (TPA) moieties, respectively. This leads to a wide absorption in the NIR light region with stabilization of the HOMO energy level in the resulting dyes, as supported by TD-DFT simulations and spectroscopic characterization. When tested as sensitizers in NiOx-based p-DSSCs, A6D (with an Acceptor- π -Donor structure) outperforms both its counterpart with a Donor- π -Donor structure (D6D) and P1, a benchmark dye in the field of p-DSSCs. With A6D dye-sensitizer the resulting DSSC device presents the quite remarkable value of stabilized efficiency as high as 0.15% when I^-/I^{3-} is employed as redox couple and nanostructured NiOx photocathode is thick less than 2 μm and does not contain any blocking layer.

Concerning the electrolytes, environmentally friendly water-based Quasi-Solid Electrolytes (QSE) for n-type DSSCs have been developed and deeply characterized. The production of the QSE hydrogels is achieved by exploiting the concept of fully green design and fabrication, through the selection of components such as the natural polysaccharide galactomannan, biocompatible zinc salts, and the employment of eco-friendly synthetic procedures to produce the hybrid gelating agents. In the process, moderate temperature (<40 °C), only aqueous solutions are employed, and, at most, ethanol is used in some phases of the procedure. Depending on the type of the initial salt,

either zinc hydroxysulfate lamellae or zinc oxide nanoparticles are created within the gel matrix, with a more extended nanoporous structure in the latter case. The nanostructures and the gels are investigated by multiple techniques, including X-ray diffraction, infrared spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy and thermogravimetric analysis. Upon ensuing addition of I⁻/I³⁻ redox mediator and assembling of the device, an unprecedented open-circuit voltage as high as 750 mV has been obtained and photovoltaic efficiency up to 2% has been achieved, comparable to state-of-the-art aqueous QSE-DSSCs. Finally, Linear Response-Time Dependent DFT simulations are carried out on a model iodine/iodide layered zinc hydroxy sulphate structure towards a better understanding of the working mechanism.

Poliba/DIMMM In the reporting period, in the context of development of innovative technologies aimed at increasing the autonomy of rovers for planetary exploration Poliba has started to investigate two issues dealing, respectively with: surface smoothing through rigid wheel interaction and harmonic artificial potential field path-planning. A novel approach is being developed to obtaining a reliable description of the surface profile after the passage of a rigid wheel in planetary exploration rovers. The method relies on a moving average filter with a window length selected according to the wheel geometry and the soil parameters. Classical terramechanical implications are considered, such as the contact between the wheel and the underlying deformed soil and the bulldozing effect. A single-wheel test bed was developed under the multibody environment MSC Adams to verify the numerical results.

Path planning is a crucial aspect of enabling autonomous navigation for mobile robots, especially in environments with obstacles and varied terrains like those encountered in space exploration. Reactive computing methods, particularly Artificial Potential Fields (APF), have been widely used for their ability to quickly respond to changing environments. However, traditional APF approaches can suffer from local minima issues and sub-optimal paths. To address this, Harmonic Artificial Potential Fields (HAPF) have been proposed as a complete and smooth alternative, but their computational complexity remains a challenge. This part of the research aims to introduce a novel approach that combines the advantages of APF for local planning with the completeness of HAPF for global planning.

Output and results:

- **Polito/DIMEAS (STAR):** Development of the calculation tools to support the early design phase of space systems. Development and first draft of the CubeSat technology database (CUTE-DB).
- **Polito/DISMA:** Development of an eXtended Finite Element scheme and prototype code for 3D-1D coupled problems.
- **Polito/DIMEAS:** Validation of the thermal models by testing in thermal chamber using a novel measurement technique via FBG optical sensors, suitable to implement an effective

thermal monitoring and control in space. Packaging techniques of FBG sensors for thermal measurement in space.

- **PoliTO/DIMEAS:** Software to optimize the design of Space Logistics missions considering low-thrust propulsion.
- **PoliTO/DET:** Taxonomy of 14 simulators/emulators to simulate the communication in satellite network.
- **LINKS/CPE:** 3D models for digital twin creation
- **UniTO/Math:** Database Creation, Clustering Development, and Visualization Tools for two and three-dimensional orbits
- **UniTO/Chemistry:** Development of two organic sensitizers based on sexithiophene chain, and different aqueous quasi-solid electrolytes based on natural polysaccharide galactomannan with zinc hydroxysulfate lamellae and zinc oxide nanoparticles.
- **PoliTO/DIMEAS (STAR):** Preliminary design of the visual navigation algorithms for proximity operations of small distributed systems. First version of the algorithms developed.
- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** preliminary analytical (Matlab) and multibody (MSC Adams) models to study the surface profile after the passage of a rigid wheel in planetary exploration.

Journal publications:

- **UniTO/Chemistry:** A. Zarate, L. Gontrani, S. Galliano, E. M. Bauer, D. T. Donia, C. Barolo, M. Bonomo, M. Carbone, "Green zinc/galactomannan-based hydrogels push up the photovoltage of quasi solid aqueous dye sensitized solar cells", *Solar Energy*, Volume 272, 2024, 112460, ISSN 0038-092X, DOI: 10.1016/j.solener.2024.112460).
- **POLITO/DISEG:** A. M. Bertetto, J. Melchiorre, G. C. Marano, "Improved multi-body rope approach for free-form gridshell structures using equal-length element strategy", *Automation in Construction*, Volume 161, 2024, 105340, ISSN 0926-5805, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2024.105340.
- **POLITO/DISMA:** Berrone, S., Grappein, D. & Scialò, S. A PDE-constrained optimization method for 3D-1D coupled problems with discontinuous solutions. *Numer Algor* 95, 499–526 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11075-023-01579-w>

Submitted publications:

- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** "Assessment of a Consistent Multi-temperature Kinetic Model for Hypersonic Neutral Air Flows using a High-order-accurate Finite Volume Solver", accepted for presentation at ICCFD12, July 14-19, 2024, Kobe, JAPAN

- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** “Atmospheric re-entry flow simulations in ionization regime”, accepted for presentation at EFDC1, 16 – 20 September 2024, Aachen, Germany
- **PoliTo/DIMEAS (STAR):** 1 conference publication (“Concurrent Model-Based Approach for CubeSat Mission Design”) accepted at IAC (International Astronautical Congress) 2024
- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** Exploring surface smoothing through rigid wheel interaction in planetary exploration rovers, submitted to IEEE CASE 2024
- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** Wheels during step-obstacle negotiation: contact forces analysis, submitted to IFTOMM IFIT 24
- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** Harmonic artificial potential field path planning for tracked robots in unstructured environments, submitted to Robotics and Autonomous Syst.

Dissemination activity:

- **PoliBA/DIMMM:** Organisation of the symposium Mobile Robot and Unmanned Ground Vehicles, at ASME 2023 IMECE International Mechanical Engineering Congress, New Orleans, Oct. 29 – Nov. 2, 2023

Deviations (if applicable):

No Deviations from initial planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTo/DIMEAS (STAR): First release of the CubeSat Technology Database (CUTE-DB). Validation of the Concurrent Engineering System (CES) tools in the reference use case selected. Integration of the CES tools with the CUTE-DB.

PoliTo/DIMEAS (STAR): Iterative review and improvement of the navigation algorithms design.

PoliTo/DIMEAS: Development of new simulations tools to deal with Space Logistics missions in Cislunar environment.

UniTo/Chemistry: Continue the development of different materials for innovative photovoltaics (e.g. dye-sensitized solar cells). In particular, the research will be focused on the synthesis and characterization of NIR organic dyes, electrolytes, and semiconductor layers (e.g. based on zinc oxides) with improved optical properties, long-term stability, and photoconversion efficiency.

UniTO/Math: Extend the database of periodic solutions, progressively increasing in complexity (e.g., by considering either a greater number of bodies in two and three dimensions, or a uniform axial rotation); Continue to develop visualization tools to display the solutions derived from the database; Start to implement machine learning techniques to generate new orbits, which may not necessarily be symmetric.

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n.2	Start month: M4	End month: M36					
Title: DEVELOPMENT							
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y/N							
RM Leader	PoliTO						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa			
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	14.99	0.4	0				

Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

Research studies to support the DEVELOPMENT phase of space systems and missions.

[Task 2.1 Manufacturing processes](#)

PoliTO/DIMEAS:

In the reporting period, the activities related to the surface plasma treatment of composite materials (carbon/glass fibres and epoxy resin matrix) were defined: preliminary tests on carbon surface treated fabrics were conducted in terms of surface chemical characterization (micro Raman, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy – Attenuated Total Reflection spectroscopy) and mechanical characterization (Double Cantilever Beam, End Notched Flexure and lately, standard 3 points flexural test) of the fabricated composites CF/Epoxy matrix. Different techniques to characterize the surface of the fibres have been analyzed, in collaboration with the DISAT department. Specifically, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) to quantify the chemical surface content after plasma treatment, Oxygen, Carbon and Nitrogen atomic percentages. This is investigated as a target to find the optimal setup of plasma treatment process parameters. To this aim, an appropriate Design of Experiment (DoE) has been analyzed and calibrated to maximize, using a Response Surface Methodology (RSM), the process output. This methodology will define the optimal parameters of the plasma treatment. Furthermore, the analysis will be carried out also by using micromechanical tests to correlate the improvements in the mechanical properties to the modification of the surface properties. This mechanical testing methodology will allow also to minimise the use of raw materials in the preliminary testing experimental campaign.

PoliTO/DISAT (LINCE):

LINCE group targeted the experimental work on the production of engineered ceramics: on one side, structural ceramics joining strength, toughness and durability as innovative high-reliable materials; on the other side, functionalized ceramics for the selective capture of CO₂ produced by human crew during space missions.

Engineered ceramics based on zirconia and mullite were successfully produced by DLP.

In the case of zirconia structural ceramics, dense ceramics with simple geometries (bars and pellets) suitable for mechanical testing were fabricated. Microstructural characterization of the sintered materials revealed the presence of flaws, like delamination, typical of the additive manufacturing technique. While flexural mechanical tests are on-going, in order to understand the role of such flaws on the structural performance of the ceramics, optimization of the whole process (powder elaboration, slurry formulation, printing parameters) is in course, to decrease the number and length of defects, with the aim of producing materials with mechanical properties comparable with those fabricated by conventional techniques.

In the case of mullite, a smart system for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) was designed and developed, through the shaping of ceramic substrates by DLP, and their subsequent functionalization for CO₂ capture with Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs), i.e. crystalline materials with ultrahigh porosity and internal surface areas. Mullite ceramics with both simple (lattice) and complex (TPMS) structures have been successfully printed. To do that, mullite slurry for DLP was prepared by mixing the ceramic powder with a photocurable acrylates-based liquid monomer, in presence of a dispersant, used to achieve proper solid loading and rheology. The printed structures were submitted to post-processing steps, such as debinding and sintering, providing systems characterized by hierarchical porosity. Large open pores were designed to maximize the permeation by gas and micrometric-sized pores to promote MOF adhesion and growth. MOF seeds were synthesized by a hydrothermal method, and MOF seeds subsequently grown on the sintered mullite structures.

PoliTO/DISAT (Glance): During this reporting period, Glance Group (DISAT) conducted a comprehensive assessment of the distributed lab's current capabilities and resources. Subsequently, Glance outlined specific initiatives focused on the study of surface plasma treatment of ceramic based materials as well as on C reinforced polymeric composite materials, in collaboration with DIMEAS department.

The activity aims at exploring plasma-based solutions for improving the joint strength of joined components by inducing a new surface texture able to promote interlocking; moreover, it pays special attention to identifying treatments that can be implemented at an industrial scale.

In particular, silicon carbide (SiC) was investigated. It is attracting a great deal of interest in advanced technological applications as aerospace, because of its outstanding thermomechanical properties and lightweight. Nevertheless, the application of SiC-based materials depends on the ability to join them, in many cases, because manufacturing these materials as large components, with complicated shapes, is extremely difficult and expensive. A critical issue for the broader use of SiC is thus the development of joining methods to assemble large components in complex structures.

To manufacture a reliable product, promoting optimal adhesion between the parts to be joined and the joining material is critical. This can be promoted by a preliminary preparation of the surface and in particular by modifying the surface texture and chemistry. We investigated the effectiveness of plasma-based solutions as techniques to improve SiC joints strength. The effectiveness of the plasma treatment to strengthen the joining can be attributed to the formation of this thin silica film, which creates a mechanical anchoring system when penetrated by the adhesive. In the reported activity, zeta potential measurements, in combination with microscopical analysis, were applied to characterize SiC surfaces and adhesive to understand more in-depth the eventual chemical interaction between the surface and the adhesive, proposing for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, this technique for characterizing surfaces and adhesives before joining.

Polito/DISEG: In terms of Team advancement, the form finding method was refined by implementing an improved formulation of the multi-body rope approach (MRA) method.

The research of the last months introduces improvements for a form-finding method for gridshell structures originally proposed by the authors and useful for space structure. Once a load condition is set, the basic MRA defines a structural geometry with minimized eccentricity of compression forces, reducing bending moments. This approach models the structure as masses connected by loose ropes, with dynamics solving yielding an equilibrium configuration. To simplify construction management and reduce computational effort, two enhancement methods are proposed for the basic MRA. The first involves grouping elements with identical lengths to minimize required structural element types. The second introduces a repulsive force field to adjust geometry, reducing unmatched components. The combination, termed i-MRA, is effective. Results also show the base mesh has minimal influence on slack coefficient trends, while the initial mesh significantly affects the final geometry. This research lays the groundwork for further exploration, including assessing method impacts on structural performance and instability, integrating into optimization procedures, and optimizing panel and node shapes. Concerning the exploration of the most suitable material for the mockup, the choice of the material proposed for the dome follows the requirements of the in-situ resource utilization (ISRU) approach. First evaluations have been done in the last weeks to use a concrete-like material using local materials for both aggregates and binder, and a proposal is made for Mars exploration. The aggregate can be made from the local regolith, whose composition can be roughly simulated by a basaltic sand, choosing the correct granulometry observed by the Mars exploration missions. Regarding the binder two possibilities are considered: a CaSO₄-based binder, that could exploit the gypsum dunes observed in the north of the planet; a binder based on iron-sulfate, that is widely spread on the surface of Mars, and that was never reported before as a possible material for Mars ISRU. Finally, considering a final material configuration also constituted by the inclusion of natural fibers in the mix,

compressive and flexural strength tests will be carried out to evaluate the response of the compounds under operating conditions of the dome compatible with the service life of the structure in the extra-terrestrial habitat.

Task 2.2 smart AIV/T

Polito/DIMEAS: The Model & Simulation Based tool (a hybrid SIL-HIL simulator) is the main tool for the verification and validation of space technologies, that is already available in the CubeSat Advanced Simulator & Test-bench (CAST) facility at DIMEAS. The existing models for GNC miniaturised systems have been updated and the simulator is able to perform the verification of visual navigation algorithms. AIV/T activities on the first version of the visual navigation algorithms developed in Task 1.4 of the Research Module 1 will be carried out.

A new model-based simulation environment that enhances the capabilities of the simulator has been identified. Its development and application to a reference use case are ongoing.

The electronics is the most important source of defects during AIV/T activities, with specific reference to soldering process. The definition of strategies for supporting the verification and testing of small space systems has been defined, with specific reference to the electronic boards, and SMD soldering process, as well as the thermal testing effectiveness. The objective is to reduce the duration and the cost of the verification/testing campaign, while increasing the effectiveness of the verification/testing activities, with the final goal of increasing mission success. In particular, a space grade representative geometry of an electronic board, and a specific soldering process, have been selected to implement a set of experiments, with statistical significance, and to study how the number and amplitude of thermal cycles can enucleate the possible defects into soldering joints. The design of experiments of the tests has been defined. Therefore, a test campaign has been planned and it will start using a thermal chamber, available at DIMEAS laboratories, to define the best defects screening technique. Contacts were made with SMEs capable of developing the electronic board and the associated soldering process that could report a high number of soldering pads in order to improve the statistical quality of the experiment. A process for generating realistic defect simulations on solder pads is being identified.

Task 2.3 ICT Technologies

Polito/DAUIN: As for the previous reporting period, research activities in ICT technologies were dedicated to investigating the fault tolerance of deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and specifically the effect of several design choices including choice of architecture, training protocol, and quantization. Despite their distributed and parallel nature, CNNs are not intrinsically tolerant to radiation-induced transient faults. Transient faults (in the form of bit flips) were simulated at

the software level after optimizing the injection technique by considering the statistical distribution of the errors.

Experiments were conducted on several publicly available datasets, from the well-known ImageNet classification task to several EO benchmarks. Design choices that were experimentally investigated included the architecture (ResNet-50, VGG13, DenseNet161, InceptionV3), choice of pre-training (standard supervised setting vs. pretraining via self-supervised learning – SSL), choice of activation clipping function (Relu6 vs. ClipAct), choice of quantization (32 bit vs. 8 bit), and their interplay. Experimental results have gained novel insights on the trade-off between accuracy and fault tolerance, and in particular of the fault tolerance of SSL pretrained networks. Preliminary results were presented at the 27th IEEE International Symposium on Design and Diagnostics of Electronic Circuits and Systems, and an extended version is being finalized for a journal submission.

PoliTO/DET: During this period the integration of the blocks of the physical layer signal simulator continued. These software elements are being integrated in the software-defined radio reconfigurable test-bench for testing communication architectures tailored to small satellites, intended for employment both within Earth's orbits and as integral communication nodes in space missions, including, but not limited to, those bound for the Moon village. Signals used for ranging channels are included as well.

The simulator is including both code ranging signals as well as Doppler based techniques. As for the navigation part, a revision of the already available Software-defined implementation of GNSS receivers was undertaken it is now integrated in in the test-bench.

PoliTO/DET: A semi-analytical approach is under development to study the performance in terms of maximum throughput and minimum communication delay to support a given data traffic matrix between pairs of ground stations. The communication at packet level is based on the store-carry-forward paradigm, by which the satellites cooperate to enable multihop communication. Furthermore, the approach exploits the deterministic mobility of the satellites to devise a specific space-time graph on which the performance can be evaluated.

PoliBA/DEI: As part of the establishment of objective criteria for the determination of radiation resistance of photonic devices, given the lack of internationally recognized specific standards, a review of standards related to semiconductors and electronic devices has been carried out. Each of these documents was examined to extract relevant criteria and methodologies that could be applied to the testing of photonic devices in terms of radiation resistance. In addition, data from test campaigns carried out by international agencies on the radiation behaviour of these devices were collected and catalogued.

Furthermore, an analysis was conducted on the software tools that can be used for the simulation of photonic devices and systems, with a particular emphasis on the analysis of the effects of gamma rays on their refractive index. A significant problem with the existing simulation software is the inability to support multilayer target simulation, necessitating modifications and adaptations to the existing code. The results suggested the need for bespoke software solutions to overcome these challenges.

Task 2.4 Generic technologies

UniTO/DipFisica: With the acquisition of an Iron55 source, the procurement of instrumentation for the enhancement of the X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF), hosted in the Physics Department of UniTO, has been completed. The radioactive source is currently employed in the comprehensive characterization of four different Gas Pixel Detectors (GPD), identical to those onboard the Imaging X-ray Polarimetry Explorer (IXPE). We have already made some preliminary tests and measured the photo-electron track length within the gas for the four available GPD. We are now starting with the energy calibration process and the gain uniformity test of pixels.

PoliBA/DEI: The activities carried out included the identification of innovative functions in space missions. The first area of interest examined is that of smart monitoring and damage detection in structures. The ability to detect damage and initiate self-repair processes is a significant advancement for space mission sustainability. Embedded sensors can detect structural damage and trigger repair mechanisms or alert ground control for intervention. Moreover, their use can lead to the development of self-healing materials, that can repair themselves after damage, reducing maintenance needs and enhancing the safety and longevity of spacecraft.

Accordingly, a review was conducted to identify the most promising results from the use of photonic sensors for structure monitoring. Fiber-optic sensors stand as a preeminent choice for monitoring conditions in severe environments, where precise measurements of temperature or strain are needed. Specifically, due to their dimensions and mass, Fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors, can be integrated into a variety of materials. Because of their embedding capability, numerous applications have been demonstrated in the marine and aerospace fields, the translation of which to space is worth exploring.

Output and results:

Research results:

- **PoliTO/DIMEAS:** Definition and preliminary application of DoE to plasma surface treatment's parameters setup; X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy development onto glass fiber fabric surface treated and untreated; 3 points flexural test performed on CF/epoxy components.
- **POLITO/DIMEAS:** Improvement of the existing CAST facility. Identification of a new model-

based simulation environment for AIV/T activities of space systems.

- **PoliTO/DET:** simulator for a network of cooperative mobile nodes

Journal publications:

- **POLITO/DISAT (GLANCE):** A. De Zanet, V. Casalegno, G. Cempura, C. Malinverni, S. Spriano, S. Ferraris, "TEM and zeta potential titration as suitable techniques for investigating the joining of modified ceramic surfaces", *Ceramics International*, Volume 50, Issue 7, Part B, 2024, Pages 11787-11794, DOI:10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.01.083.

Conference publications:

- **PoliTO/DAUIN:** R. Milazzo, V. De Marco, C. De Sio, S. Fosson, L. Morra, L. Sterpone, "On the Fault Tolerance of Self-Supervised Training in Convolutional Neural Networks", 27th IEEE International Symposium on Design and Diagnostics of Electronic Circuits and Systems, Kielce (Poland), 3-5 April 2024

Presentations at Conferences:

- **PoliTO/DISAT (LINCE):** Part of these results was presented as oral contributions to the 18th European Inter-Regional Conference on Ceramics (CIEC18, Lausanne, Switzerland, 6-8 February 2024).
- **UniTO/DipFisica:** 1 poster at "IFAE 2024" (Florence, 3-5 April 2024)

Submitted publications:

- **PoliTo/DISAT (GLANCE):** 1 paper ("TEM and Zeta potential titration as suitable techniques for investigating the joining of modified ceramic surfaces.") under Review on *Ceramics International* (Q1)
- **PoliTo/DIMEAS:** 1 paper submitted ("Effect of the atmospheric plasma treatment parameters on the surface and mechanical properties of carbon fabric.") on MDPI journal; 1 conference paper submitted at International Symposium on Dynamic Response and Failure of Composite Materials 2024.

Deviations (if applicable):

NONE

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO/DISAT (LINCE): Characterization of the MOF-functionalized mullite system in terms of CO₂ capture, and set-up of the regeneration conditions of the device. Optimization of the printing

conditions of the structural zirconia-based ceramics to limit the flaws and maximize the mechanical performance.

At the same time, a scientific collaboration with experts of Computational Fluid Dynamic has been launched. This collaboration will be precious for supporting the design of porous ceramic substrates maximizing their permeability, avoiding time-consuming trial and errors approaches. Micro-CT and permeability/adsorption testing for evaluating the gas capture efficacy will be evaluated.

PoliTO/DISAT (GLANCE): In the next months, the following activities will be carried out

- Further characterization of surface modified SiC -based materials
- Comparison of morphologies and mechanical strength in SiC based joints with and without surface modification
- characterisation of surface modified samples (CFRP) developed in collaboration with DIMEAS department
- definition of a methodology for the plasma surface modification of ceramic substrates to promote MOFs growth, in collaboration with Lince group (DISAT).

PoliTO/DIMEAS (STAR): Test campaign of the first version of the visual navigation algorithms through the CAST facility. Development of a new model-based simulation environment for the validation and testing of space systems.

PoliTO/DIMEAS: implementation and verification of the DoE; comparison of the spectroscopic surface characterization methodologies already implemented with similar and different types thanks to the collaboration with the DISAT department.

PoliTO/DAUIN: Research activities have been carried out so far by considering a simplified fault model in which multiple bit flips are independently applied to the networks weights and biases. We are currently investigating the applicability of more realistic fault models. Secondly, given that quantized DNNs have shown strong fault-tolerance properties, but very variable performances in terms of accuracy, we plan to investigate how to improve the accuracy/fault-tolerance trade-off for this type of DNNs. Third, we will extend the analysis to other network architectures beyond CNNs.

PoliTO/DET: finalisation of the signal simulator including both the physical layer and the networking layer

1.2.2 Research Module 3

Research Module n.3	Start month: M4			End month: M36			
Title: OPERATIONS							
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y/N							
RM Leader	PoliTO						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa			
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	1.31	0.0	0.0				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
Research studies to support the OPERATIONS phase of space systems and missions.							
<u>Task 3.1 Autonomous operation</u>							
Activities for this task are scheduled to start later in the project.							
<u>Task 3.2 Ground infrastructure</u>							
PoliTO/DIMEAS (STAR): The operations management system (or Mission Control Centre – MCC) of the CubeSat Control Centre – C3 has been finalised and tested in operative conditions on a real application, that is the Spei Satelles mission, since June 2023. The system has been used to prepare commands and to process housekeeping and mission data. The C3 MCC at PoliTO is composed of core software managing the interaction with the operators, the generation of the command to be sent to the radio interfaces, and the storage and analysis of the raw data. If the received packets are not corrupted, they are decoded, and the values are displayed in real-time on a dedicated window. On the other hand, if the packets are not decodable, they are automatically saved in various formats, allowing post-processing and decoding. Other functions of the MCC software are the coordination of tracking tasks and the management of the radiofrequency front-end. The C3 MCC is currently operative, receiving and handling hundreds of packets from the Spei Satelles mission every day.							
The radiofrequency part of C3 has also been tested in the STARlab, while the Ground to Space (G2S) and Space to Ground (S2G) radiofrequency chains are still to be tested. Procedures for the validation of the C3 RF chains have been developed, which will be used when the C3 UHF antenna and RF equipment will be integrated.							
<u>Task 3.3 Data management</u>							
PoliTO/DISMA: In some applications huge numbers of features are used to describe real phenomena, and realistically, many of such features are redundant, with the consequence that any model or algorithm describing the phenomena might suffer of this redundancy, which							

mathematically translates in noise. Many feature reduction schemes are available in literature, and usually, linear reduction schemes are used to select a reduced number of features which are then considered as inputs of highly non linear models, as neural networks. Hence, we want to define a new feature reduction scheme which is tailored for the considered models (e.g. neural networks). We introduced a new approach to feature ranking for classification tasks, called greedy feature selection. In statistical learning, feature selection is usually realized by means of methods that are independent of the classifier applied to perform the prediction using that reduced number of features. Instead, greedy feature selection identifies the most important feature at each step and according to the selected classifier. The benefits of such scheme have been investigated theoretically in terms of model capacity indicators, such as the Vapnik-Chervonenkis (VC) dimension or the kernel alignment, and tested numerically by considering its application to the problem of predicting geo-effective manifestations of the active Sun.

PoliTO/DAUIN: Data management innovation is nowadays driven by the application of AI/ML/DL solutions for several applications that require, fast and reliable analysis of large amount of data, statistical characterization, and automated decision support. In this context, it is envisioned that data processing will be performed both on board and/or on ground. Activities on this task focused primarily on the robustness of on-board processing, in connection with activities on Task 2.3. Specifically, experiments were conducted to investigate the effectiveness of self-supervised pretraining (SSL) and quantization on accuracy and robustness of convolutional neural networks for EO tasks. We further conducted experiments on techniques that combine fault-aware training and quantization-aware training with SSL learning . A journal submission is currently being prepared on this topic.

Output and results:

Research results:

- **PoliTO/DIMEAS (STAR):** C3 MCC currently operative, handling thousands of packets received from space. Development of procedures for the validation of C3 radiofrequency chains.
- **Polito/DISMA:** Prototype code for greedy feature selection

Submitted publications:

- **PoliTo/DIMEAS (STAR):** 1 conference publication (“Integration and Testing Campaign of an educational Satellite Ground Station”) accepted at IAC (International Astronautical Congress) 2024

Deviations (if applicable):

Task 3.1 shifted to start from M12 to M18

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO/DIMEAS (STAR): Integration of the C3 UHF antenna and RF equipment and validation of the C3 radiofrequency chains. Improvement of the C3 MCC functionalities.

1.2.2 Research Module 4

Research Module n.4	Start month: M4			End month: M36			
Title: EXPLOITATION							
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y/N							
RM Leader	PoliTO						
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa			
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	7.75	0.4	0.2				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
Research studies to support the EXPLOITATION phase of space systems and missions.							
<u>Task 4.1. Modern satellite communication services</u>							
<p>PoliTO/DET: Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) based on satellite communications can be integrated in 5G and Beyond-5G (B5G) networks, by complementing the existing and future telecommunication infrastructure on the Earth. The specific, periodic mobility of satellites is exploited to devise a simulation model which is scalable, tailored for mega constellations, and which evaluates the maximum capacity between any ground station, taking into account the possible traffic congestion on the routing paths.</p>							
<u>Task 4.2 Earth Observation</u>							
<p>PoliTO/DIMEAS: Spatial interpolation techniques for the mapping of offshore parameters have been further developed and tested using simulated datasets and earth observation satellite data. The following altimeters have been used: Jason-1, Jason-2, Envisat, CryoSat-2, SARAL/AltiKa, Jason-3, CFOSAT, Sentinel-3A, Sentinel-3B, Hai Yang-2B, Sentinel-6A, Hai Yang-2C. Level 3 datasets have been accessed from Copernicus Marine Service. Furthermore, a validation dataset has been generated based on openly-available in-situ instruments of wave and wind parameters. Effort has been first directed towards the processing and generation of a database for seamlessly handling both satellite and in-situ data. Then, the performance of the algorithms, previously tested with numerical dataset alone, has been quantified. The performance remains consistent also with satellite measurements, confirming the good potential of approach herein proposed.</p>							
<p>LINKS/ADS: Our recent activities have focused on acquiring 3D point cloud data in urban areas with the support of DIST. These data sets serve for training various machine learning models aimed at identifying key elements of the urban landscape, including streets, green spaces, and buildings. The ultimate goal of this approach is to provide rapid and precise city landscape</p>							

mapping to better support urban renewal processes. Initial experiments have yielded promising results, indicating the potential of this methodology. However, further exploration and refinement are required to fully harness its capabilities. Next steps foresee the application of the most recent SotA approaches such as LCPFormer, and the integration of additional aerial 3D data for urban mapping.

Polito/DIST: In the Torino urban area, an ambitious initiative has been underway to transform the city's management and maintenance systems through technological innovation. At the forefront of this transformation are the development and application of high-resolution 3D digital models, which have provided an unprecedented level of detail in the visualization of the cityscape. The acquisition has been derived by a high res aerial dataset (5 cm GSD) embedding all the Torino municipality complemented by a high density Lidar survey (30-40 points/m²) over the same area; data processing devoted to the production of a true digital orthophoto, a high density 3D point clouds and a high res (5 cm) photorealistic 3D mesh. These models are a product of the latest advancements in photogrammetry and LIDAR scanning, offering a virtual blueprint of Torino that can be used to enhance a range of urban planning processes. The virtual models serve as a precursor to the implementation of Urban Digital Twins, a digital mirror of the city that enables real-time monitoring and simulation-based planning enabled by the definition of a publication environment based on an open source architecture for 3D photorealistic mesh deployment. These twins are instrumental in redefining how Torino addresses the maintenance of its infrastructure, particularly roads and green areas, by allowing for proactive and preventative care of these crucial urban elements. In parallel with these efforts, Torino has been proactive in its approach to energy transition. By harnessing the capability of the Urban Digital Twins, the city has embarked on a thorough assessment of photovoltaic potential. This analysis aims to pinpoint optimal locations for solar energy generation, thus propelling Torino towards a more sustainable future. Moreover, the initiative includes a comprehensive review of building energy efficiency practices, contributing to the overall reduction of the city's carbon footprint and enhancing the energy performance of its buildings. Together, these efforts represent a holistic approach to urban management, weaving the fabric of a smarter, more responsive, and sustainable Torino. The city stands as a living laboratory, a testament to how digital advancements can be harmoniously integrated into the urban fabric to foster a better quality of life for its residents.

[Task 4.3 Navigation and Geo-Positioning services](#)

Polito/DET: During the last six months the work addressing the design of modern Leo-PNT architectures continued, considering, for the candidates modulations previously identified and their performance in term of ranging capabilities. Both Code based positioning techniques as well

and Doppler based positioning strategies were considered implementing a trade-off study on the radius of the constellation (altitude of the satellite). The work is part of a Journal publication under preparation.

The GNSS monitoring station named N-SMART (Navigation Signals Monitoring, Analysis, and Recording Tool) has been installed as part of a test-bench for GNSS receivers in the lab shared with LINKS/ADS, and it's being used to test the robustness of various receivers to different jamming attacks. From the scientific point of view, the experimental facility is being used to assess the performance of the machine learning engine based on Convolutional Neural Networks to detect and classify different GNSS jamming signal injected on top of real GNSS signals.

LINKS/ADS:

As for the previous reporting period, in close collaboration with PoliTO/DET, the work on the creation of a laboratory infrastructure to support GNSS signal analysis has continued. With respect to the work reporting period, from the laboratory setup most of the effort has been dedicated to configuring the hardware infrastructure with the purpose of supporting a high level of configurability and flexibility to fast configure a test to analyse the impact of jamming and/or spoofing on GNSS receivers. LINKS team is collaborating hand to hand with researchers from Polito to investigate low complexity AI based solution to provide an early detection of interference affecting the RF signal on GNSS L1/E1 band. The current approach is willing to analyze through an LSTM neural network deviation from the expected received signal when no interference is present. Such an approach will potentially require a computational capacity which could fit on an embedded device and allow for a second detection/classification of jamming or spoofing with more sophisticated and suitable solutions. A brand-new activity has been launched and it is the refactoring and polishing of the NGene GPS+Galileo fully software receivers developed as a joint asset LINKS+PoliTo with the purpose of making an open source release free for research purposes. At the time of writing this reporting the activity has just been kick offed and a preliminary identification of the requirements and needs of the changes and adjustment required to release this new version of NGene has been addressed. Finally, alongside the release of the software the work on NGene is also willing to produce a white paper to promote the initiative

Task 4.4. Space Exploration

PoliTO/DET: The implementation of the simulator implementing the architecture and functionalities of the LUNANET both for the communication and navigation services, started.

UniTO/Dept. Physics: A first-generation Gas Pixel Detector (GPD), identical to those onboard the Imaging X-ray Polarimetry Explorer (IXPE), are undergoing long-term testing in our X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF). The objective of this study is the evaluation of GPD stability over extended durations.

Moreover, XCF is actively investigating possible improvements for future X-ray polarimetry missions. In particular in the last months we have measured the transparency of different Beryllium windows in order to select the best solution for future X-ray detectors.

Output and results:

Research results

POLITO/DET: Integration of the GNSS Monitoring station in the lab test-bench. One Journal papers submitted on the topic

LINKS/ADS: Improvement in the configurability of the laboratory setup. Preliminary test on AI algorithms for detection of RF GNSS interferences characterized by low-complexity and low computational capacity.

PoliTO/DIST: high resolution 3D model and Digital twin implementation.

Journal publications

- **POLITO/DET and LINKS/ADS** Troglia Gamba, M.; Polidori, B.D.; Minetto, A.; DAVIS, F.; Banfi, E.; Dominici, F., GNSS Radio Frequency Interference Monitoring from LEO Satellites: An In-Laboratory Prototype. *Sensors*, 2024, 24, 508. Doi: 10.3390/s24020508

Presentation at conference

UniTO/DipFisica: 1 oral contribution at "Physics Forum 2023" (San Diego, 11-13 December 2023)

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations from initial planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

- Hardware for the implementation of the GNSS monitoring station (N-SMART)

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO DET and LINKS/ADS: prosecution of the test campaign using the implemented N-SMART station to test the algorithms for interference detection and classification of GNSS interference.

UniTO/Physics Application of the designed algorithm to detectors tested in the XCF lab.

PoliTO/DET: on-going development of the simulation model for the performance evaluation of satellite networks.

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects in the period:

		In the reporting period	Since the beginning of the project
Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	0	2
	Number of publications	4 journal publications 1 conference publication	10 journal publications 4 conferences publications
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)		1 Spinoff: MESPAC s.r.l. 2 patent applications: 102023000019161, 102023000011844
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved		46
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project		57,22

2. IMPACT

The outcomes expected from the development of the Space4You lab is of course the creation of a new asset in the ecosystem. The actions taken in the research module 0 will foster its sustainability beyond the duration of this specific project, making it a reference point for the research in the Space field. The pilot projects funded to the SMEs will provide proof-of-concepts, pre-developments, innovative technologies, that will represent the tangible results of the work that has been possible thanks to the support of Space4You in terms of knowledge and facilities, and such innovative solution that can then be further developed by each participant.

This meets the NODES's objective of fostering joint research and innovative activities by universities and companies as well as increasing the business potential in terms of creation and acceleration of high- tech start-ups, development of new/enhanced product/services and/or improved industrial process.

The applications of space technologies and data can generate impacts across multiple fields of interest for the ecosystems and the related spokes, including precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, new services for mobility, new services for heritage and cultural assets, thus enlarging the range of potential involved SMEs beyond the classical pool of aerospace companies.

Space4You will be also specifically promoted towards university spin-offs. University spin-off to foster their consolidation in terms of knowledge and innovative solutions, jointly with the actions of the other boosters of the spoke that will address other aspects needed to bring them to maturity.

The creation of new innovative businesses in aerospace will be boosted by the European Space Agency Business Incubation Center Turin (ESABIC Turin www.esabic-turin.it), launched in 2021 and managed by I3P – the Business Incubator of Politecnico di Torino, in partnership with Politecnico di Torino and LINKS foundation. The ESABIC Turin supports new space-related ventures operating both in upstream and downstream space segments and has gathered a very large network of supporting corporates, research centers, financial operators and investment funds. ESABIC Turin will represent a local key asset for the translation of applied research outcomes into new high-growth businesses. and it will represent a natural further opportunity for the spin-offs that will benefit of the Space4You support.

3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc)

During this reporting period the work has been focused on the set-up of the two pilot projects, involving companies that could benefit of the Space4You facilities.

The first pilot project involves the company Synchropal, a start-up company currently part of the ESA BIC Turin, with specific needs to test the robustness of their technological solution which is an integrated GNSS receiver for timing applications. The pilot project addresses a test campaign that will exploit the test-bench created within NODES in the lab shared between POLITO/DET and LINKS ADS (see task 4.3 Navigation and Geo-Positioning services). The ability of the lab facility to represent a large number of jamming and spoofing attacks to the real GNSS signals, will be used to test the vulnerabilities of the solution and provide scientific consultancy on possible improvements of the products. Description of the activities of the pilot project is going to be detailed in deliverable D2.

The second pilot project involves the company Ellena S.p.A., a SME active in the field of aerospace manufacturing. More in details, the company has developed, upon Politecnico di Torino requirements, some specimens that have been equipped by FBG sensors to explore the integration of sensing functionalities to monitor the state of health of lunar space infrastructures. The specimens have been manufactured with advanced additive manufacturing technology. The pilot project addresses a test campaign that will exploit the test-bench created within NODES in the lab of POLITO/DIMEAS.

In terms of involvement of the industrial system, the NODES partners involved in Space4You have a network of large and small enterprises with whom they collaborate constantly, some of these being key players in the Space field. It has to be remarked that thanks to the cascade calls, the results of which have been published at the beginning of April, a subset of such companies has been identified, and it will be the main target for the activities of the next months, figuring out the best way to support their projects through the Space4You facilities.

4. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

N/A

5. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Description of Open Science Practises adopted in the reporting period and Data Management Plan updates (if applicable). Table in annexes.

6. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

Space4You aims at providing access to leading edge technologies and infrastructures, being a reference point for the company in the territory and beyond.

ANNEXES

A) LIST OF DELIVERABLES

The labels used mean:

Public — fully open; Sensitive — limited; R – Restricted; C – Confidential; S – Secret.

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
D1	Space4You Lab description	RM0	PoliTO	R	PU	M7	M9	M14 (30/11/2023)	Delivered	Description of the organisational setup of the lab
D2	Space4You Lab User Guide	RM0	PoliTO	R	SEN	M15 (draft) M36 (final)	M24 (draft) M36 (final)		In progress	Description of the lab facilities and expertise
D3	Space4You Executive Summary Report	RM0	PoliTO	R	PU	M36 (final)	M36 (final)			Description of the pilot projects completed within the activity of the lab
D4	Space4You website	RM0	PoliTo	O	PU	M7 (draft) M36 (final)	M18 (draft) M36 (final)		In progress	Accessible database of competencies and skills available in the research aerospace ecosystem

Table 1: Deliverables

B) LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
MS0	Milestone 0	RM0	PolITO		M3	M4	M4 (31/01/2023)	YES	Preparation of activity
MS1	Milestone 1	RM0	PolITO	Issue of deliverable D1 Issue of draft version of deliverable D4	M7	M14		YES	Achievement of the milestone is claimed as D1 has been delivered and a description of D4 is available on the NODES webpage
MS2	Milestone 2	RM0	PolITO	Issue of draft version of deliverable D2 Setup of 2 (TBC) pilot projects	M15	M24			Achievement of the milestone will be delayed due to the delay in the delivery of D2 and the setup of the pilot projects
MS3	Milestone 3	RM0	PolITO	Issue of final version of deliverables D2, D3 and D4	M36	-			No delay expected as of today

Table 2: Milestones

C) LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

Risk No	Description of risk	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
01	Non-fulfilment or poor engagement of partners on tasks <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Severity: Low</i>	YES	NO	-
02	Partner withdrawal <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Severity: Low</i>	YES	NO	
03	Potential impact of COVID-19 pandemic on project implementation. <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Severity: Medium</i>	YES	NO	
04	Impact of the global economic crisis and ongoing shortage of electrical components and hardware needed for the setting of the lab facilities <i>Likelihood: High</i> <i>Severity: High</i>	YES	NO	

Table 3: Risks

D) PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT: RESULTS

Name	Result type	TRLs	Steps undertaken towards exploitation (multiple choice)	Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)
Space4You lab	INFRA	TRL7	Prototyping in laboratory environment Pilot, demonstration or testing Intellectual property management Market Study Other	Emerging

Table 4:Results

E) PUBLICATIONS

Type of publication	Peer review	Type of PID (repository or y)	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of chapter not of book)	PID of publisher version of record	ISSN/ eSSN (if book insert ISBN)	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/ Year of publication	PID of book (if book chapter)	Book title (if book chapter)	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	License type CC BY or equivalent] [CC BY NC or equivalent] [CC BY NC ND or equivalent] [Other licences]
Conference proceeding	YES	DOI		doi:10.36688/ewtec-2023-619	On spatial interpolation of ocean energy source variables: A comparative analysis			L. Gambarelli, E. Pasta, and G. Giorgi	Proceedings of the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference	Vol. 15]	Energy and Climate Change Division at the University of Southampton	09/2023			NO	[
Article in journal	YES	DOI		Doi: 10.1007/s10961-023-10029-7	When computer science is not enough: universities knowledge specializations behind artificial intelligence startups in Italy			Colombelli, A., D'Amico, E. & Paolucci, E.	The Journal of Technology Transfer		Springer Nature	08/2023			YES	
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2023.1242480	Vat-photopolymerization of ceramic materials: exploring current applications in advanced multidisciplinary fields			Elisa Fiume, Bartolomeo Coppola, Laura Montanaro, Paola Palmero	Frontiers in materials		Frontiers Media S.A.	10/2023			YES	Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY)
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		DOI:10.3934/mine.2023099	The mixed virtual element discretization for highly-anisotropic problems: the role of the boundary degrees of freedom			Stefano Berrone, Stefano Scialò and Gioana Teora	Mathematics in Engineering	5	AIMS press	10/2023				Creative Commons Attribution License CC BY 4.0 DEED
Article in Journal	YES				3D printing to support experimental activities: lessons learned from rapid		ISSN 1590-8844	Berri, Pier Carlo, Dalla Vedova, Matteo D. L., Aimasso, Alessandro,	International Journal of Mechanics and Control	24	Levrotto e Bella	2023				

					prototyping of an electromechanical actuator gearbox			Ferro, Carlo G., Maggiore, Paolo, Riva, Guido,							
Conference proceeding	YES				Experimental analysis of FBG sensors thermal calibration under different loading conditions	ISBN: 978-1-6654-5690-6	Aimasso, Alessandro; Gallone, Giacomo; Dalla Vedova, M. D. L.; Maggiore, Paolo	10th IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace, MetroAeroSpace 2023	IEEE		2023				
Conference proceeding	YES				Creation of a Support Software for the Development of a System for Sending and Visualizing FBG Sensor Data for Aerospace Application	ISBN: 978-1-6654-5690-6	Antonio Costantino Marceddu, Alessandro Aimasso, Antonio Scaldaferrì, Paolo Maggiore, Bartolomeo Montrucchio, Matteo D. L. Dalla Vedova	10th IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace, MetroAeroSpace 2023	IEEE		2023				
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		https://doi.org/10.3390/s24020508	GNSS Radio Frequency Interference Monitoring from LEO Satellites: An In-Laboratory Prototype.	ISSN 1424-8220	Troglia Gamba, M.; Polidori, B.D.; Minetto, A.; Dovi, F.; Banfi, E.; Dominici, F.	Sensors		2024, 24, 508.	MDPI		2024	YES	Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY)
Conference proceeding	YES				On the Fault Tolerance of Self-Supervised Training in Convolutional Neural Networks		Milazzo, Rosario; De Marco, Vincenzo; De Sio, Corrado; Fossion, Sophie; Morra, Lia; Sterpone, Luca	27th International Symposium on Design and Diagnostics of Electronic Circuits and Systems	IEEE		2024				
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.01.083	TEM and zeta potential titration as suitable techniques for investigating the joining of modified ceramic surfaces		Alessandro De Zanet, Valentina Casalegno, Grzegorz Cempura, Carla Malinverni, Silvia Spriano, Sara Ferraris	Ceramics International		50 (7)	Elsevier		2024	yes	Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY)
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		https://doi.org/10.1007/s11075-023-01579-w	A PDE-constrained optimization method for 3D-1D coupled problems with discontinuous solutions		Stefano Berrone, Denise Grappein, Stefano Scialò	Numerical Algorithms			Springer		2024		

Article in Journal	YES	DOI		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2024.112460	Green zinc/galactomannan-based hydrogels push up the photovoltage of quasi solid aqueous dye sensitized solar cells	ISSN 0038092X	Segura Zarate, Ana Yancy; Gontrani, Lorenzo; Galliano, Simone; Bauer, Elvira Maria; Donia, Domenica Tommasa; Barolo, Claudia; Bonomo, Matteo; Carbone, Marilena	Solar Energy	Vol 272, Art. number 112460	Elsevier	Apr-24	YES	Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY)
--------------------	-----	-----	--	---	---	---------------	---	--------------	-----------------------------	----------	--------	-----	--

Table 5: Publications

F) DATASETS

Table 6: Data sets

Short Name:	SpaceStartups
Description of datasets:	Data regarding founding teams of 339 EU-based start-ups in the New Space sector. Data were collected from the Dealroom.com database for companies founded between 2013 and 2022, with at least €1 million in funding received. Data were collected from the Dealroom database. Firm-level data have been then integrated with individual data on the characteristics of the founders using information from LinkedIn. Each startup has been classified according to a large set of variables that include technological and industrial specialization, economic performance, fundraising capabilities, links with academic and industrial partners, geographical location, the educational and work background of the founders.
Data origin:	Dealroom.com and LinkedIn.com
Data type:	String; Integer; Boolean;Float
Data Formats:	.dta

Useful for whom:	The data were used by the DIGEP research group and were needed to validate the conclusions of a scientific publication
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	open access given data
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	SpaceStartups.dta
Accessibility:	Fully open repository
Interoperability:	Standards for interoperability
Reusability:	Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation
Open	YES

Short Name:	SpaceInvestors
Description of datasets:	Investor data from 339 EU-based start-ups in the new space sector. Data was collected and complemented on the basis of the 'SpaceStartup' database. The company-level data was then supplemented with individual investor data using LinkedIn information. Each investor was classified according to type, e.g. venture capital, angel investor, etc.
Data origin:	Dealroom.com and LinkedIn.com
Data type:	String; Integer; Boolean; Float

Data Formats:	.dta
Useful for whom:	The data were used by the DIGEP research group and were needed to validate the conclusions of a scientific publication
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	open access given data
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	SpaceInvestors.dta
Accessibility:	Fully open repository
Interoperability:	Standards for interoperability
Reusability:	Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation
Open	YES

G) INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Type of IP Rights	Application Title	Application Reference	Application Date	IPR Owner	IPR Status Has protection been awarded?	IPR Award Reference ID
Patent	Sistema e metodo per la determinazione di dati meteorologici e/o ambientali di un sito di interesse	IT 102023000019161	18/09/2023	Mattiazzo Giuliana, Giorgi Giuseppe, Cervelli Giulia, Pasta Edoardo, Gulisano Andrea	NO	-
Patent	Metodo ed apparato per la stabilizzazione di formazioni di satelliti	IT102023000011844	09/06/2023	Stefano Aliberti, Riccardo Apa, Catello Leonardo Matonti, Marcello Romano	NO	-

Table 7: IPRs

H) OTHER RESULTS

Type of result	Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form?	TRLs	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for the result service/webpage hosting the result (if available)	What license is the result under
Software	DroneSim Simulator of a network of mobile nodes		TRL2			https://github.com/paolo-giaccone/DronetSim/	Open source: GNU General Public License v2.0
Software	Routines for numerical computations of stability indicators to facilitate the clustering of the orbits		TRL2			https://github.com/LimenResearch/norbit	Open source: GNU General Public License v2.0
Prototype	N-SMART: GNSS monitoring station		TRL 7				

Table 8: Other results

I) IMPACT in terms of TRLs, SDGs, KSOs

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: TR2-TRL3 Current status: TRL 4	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]

Table 9: TRLs

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality	[Not relevant]
Clean Water and Sanitation	[Not relevant]
Life Below Water	[Not relevant]
Life on Land	[Partially relevant]
No Poverty	[Not relevant]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant]
Good Health and Well-being	[Partially relevant]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant]

Decent Work and Economic Growth	[Full relevant]
Affordable and Clean Energy	[Not relevant]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	[[Full relevant]
Reduced Inequality	[Not relevant]
Sustainable Cities and Communities	[Partially relevant]
Responsible Consumption and Production	[Not relevant]
Quality Education	[Full relevant]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant]
International cooperation	Full relevant]
Please explain your choice:	The Space4You lab aims at improving the technological capabilities of the industry creating a shared virtual and physical space where it can meet the applied research world. In this view it will contribute to the competitiveness of the companies involved fostering their economic growth. It is a space where improving education and training of students and young professionals. Space is by definition and “international environment” that requires international cooperation, especially in the research field. Last but not least all the downstream applications of space (communications, Navigation, Earth Observation) contribute to services that improve the quality of life and the development of sustainable services

Table 10: SDGs

Horizon Europe KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS (KSO)	Horizon Europe Impact Areas	Contribution to the KSO and the relevant expected impacts
KSO 1 Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital and enabling technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations	A competitive and secure data-economy	
	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	
	Secure and cyber secure digital technology	
	High quality digital services for all	
KSO 2 Restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment	Enhancing ecosystems and biodiversity on land and in waters	
	Clean and healthy air, water and soil	Earth observation applications have great impact in environmental monitoring
	Sustainable food systems and nutrition security	Satellite Navigation and Earth observation applications foster the development of sustainable services (e.g smart farming and agriculture)
KSO 3 Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	
	Affordable and clean energy	
	Smart and sustainable transport	Satellite Navigation and communications foster the development of sustainable services in transport market
	Circular and clean	

	economy	
KSO 4 Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society , prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health	A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats	

Table 11: KSOs and Impact Areas - HE